

Melanoma And Variant Effects: beyond sunscreen
Episode 2 Transcript and Show Notes

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Facilitated by the Atlas of Variant Effect Alliance

Episode 2 Transcript

Alex Nguyen Ba: Welcome back to the Variants and Us podcast! I'm Alex, a professor at the University of Toronto, and the team: Evelina, Kortni, Adrine, and Moez, consists of scientists working at the forefront of research in the field of genetics. We work in research labs on variant interpretation - that is, we examine the effect that mutations have on our genes with the ultimate goal of understanding the genetic basis of diseases. In the first episode, we focused on genetic variants and rare diseases, but today we want to explore how DNA can predispose people to a much more common disease: skin cancer.

Kortni Kindree: We would like to note that this podcast focuses on a realistic portrayal of the basic research behind rare diseases and cancer with the hope that it will lead to better patient care, but this podcast is not meant to be medical advice.

[Intro music plays]

Evelina Tronina: Today we are speaking to two internationally recognized researchers who explore how DNA variants can affect cancer risk, and how technology has evolved to study this predisposition on a large scale.

Kortni: Have you ever wondered why skin cancer rates vary depending on where you live? Our first specialist, Dr. Dave Adams, was born in Australia, which has one of the highest rates of skin cancer in the world.

Evelina: Hi Dr. Adams, can you introduce yourself and your research?

Dr. Dave Adams: Yeah, thanks so much for inviting me to talk with the podcast. So I'm Australian, as you probably gathered from my accent. I grew up in a farming area in Australia and was always interested in science and I went to the University of Sydney, and I did my training there, and a PhD there. And then I thought I was going to end up in Houston, in Texas, but Alan Bradley who was at Houston at the time, moved to become the director of the Sanger Institute, so I joined him here in Cambridge, UK. And that was 22 years ago, and I've been at the Wellcome Sanger Institute ever since. And I'm now a senior group leader in the cancer aging and somatic mutation program.

Kortni: Can you explain how the country you live in and your skin type can affect your cancer risk?

DA: In Australia we talk about the most lethal type of skin cancer, which is called melanoma, as being Australia's cancer. And we say that because it's a sunny country, and we know that ultraviolet light is linked to an increased risk. But the other thing about risk of melanoma is the type of skin that you have. So people who are like me, pale and freckly with blue eyes, are at much greater risk of getting skin cancer than someone else in the general population. And this is in the order of somewhere between 2 and 4 fold increased risk based on that common genetic predisposition.

Then beyond that, there's roughly 10% of patients or 10% of individuals who are very highly predisposed to developing melanoma, and this can be because of a mutation in a range of different genes.

Evelina: Going out into the sun can make us feel good and energized, but what happens in our cells? Ultra Violet (or UV) rays emitted by the sun are very high in energy, and can enter our skin cells and cause damage to our DNA.

Kortni: Indeed, the DNA can break, or be chemically altered by UV light, causing changes in the original sequence, which may become harmful in the long term. Luckily, we have evolved some mechanisms to mitigate this damage, for example by producing melanin.

Evelina: Melanin (not to be confused with melatonin, the sleep hormone) is a pigment that can absorb UV light and protect your cells from DNA damage. It also gives your skin, hair, and eyes their colour. Caucasian populations have less melanin and are therefore more susceptible to some forms of skin cancer, like melanoma.

Kortni: That is why some people can have a nice tan after a day at the beach, but others will experience sunburns, pain, and peeling of the skin. It is all in our genes.

Evelina: But beyond that, what other genes play a role in determining our risk of melanoma?

DA: One of them is called CDKN2A, another is called BAP1, and there's another one called POT1, which is a gene that we identified in the lab several years ago. And these account for, as I said roughly 10% of cases of melanoma plus leukaemias, brain tumors, and other malignancies as well, pancreatic cancer in some patients.

Kortni: How did you first notice that individuals with mutations in POT1 actually had a higher risk of skin cancer?

DA: We have a wonderful set of collaborations around the world as part of a consortia, which is called GenoMEL, which is all of the dermatologists and oncologists who are involved in treating patients who have germline predispositions to melanoma come together.

Evelina: The reproductive cells, like eggs and sperm, are often referred to as germline cells. If one of your parent's germ cells had a mutation, you will inherit this mutation in every cell that makes up your body.

DA: ...And from that group we were able to collect several hundred families who had a strong history of melanoma, and then we sequenced them. And actually, another member of the AVE alliance, Daniela Robles who is involved, she was a PhD student in my group at the time, and one Thursday afternoon we were sitting in my office looking at the data that we got from the sequencing and we noticed that there were a couple of families where there were variants in this POT1 gene that were in all of the affected cases, but not in the non-affected cases, and that was the first clue that we had.

Kortni: The Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance, or AVE (our sponsor) is dedicated to fostering collaboration so that scientists around the world can work together to understand the effects mutations have on the human genome. If you want to know more about this you can listen to our first episode!

Evelina: So getting back to POT1, what exactly is its role in cells? Is it related to melanin production or something else?

DA: Yeah. So the POT1 is involved in regulating telomeres, it is involved in 2 aspects of telomere function. The first is involved in the DNA damage response of telomere ends, and the second is in regulating telomere length.

Kortni: The human genome is separated into 46 chromosomes, which are essentially very long strands of DNA. Telomeres are long and repetitive segments of DNA located at each end of these strands. They prevent information from being lost when DNA is copied during cell division, as they contain no important genes, so the loss of a few bases is not crucial. With aging, telomeres are shortened as each cell division causes a loss of a few bases at the end.

Evelina: Dr. Adams, can you expand more on how you related telomere length to disease?

DA: So when I was a genetics student, I was always taught that short telomeres were a bad thing, and they definitely are. But what we showed, and others have subsequently followed to show is that really long telomeres are a bad thing, too. So these patients have telomeres that can be 3, 4, 5 times longer than the average population, and intriguingly they get melanoma, they get types of leukemia like chronic lymphocytic leukemia as well, and there is some evidence to suggest they can also get brain tumors. And then I started to think, well, long telomeres, how does that link to cancer at all? And over time we built our confidence in the fact that it was a real result, and subsequently it's been linked to a range of different conditions. We also had a number of families where we had variants that we knew were disease-causing because we had lots of phenotyping data on those patients, we had pedigrees.

Evelina: Dr. Adams is referring to a phenotype, which is the observed trait that is produced by your genes. One example is skin and hair colour, which we have already mentioned. A darker colour is the result of increased melanin production, which is encoded by genes.

Kortni: Another observed trait can be a greater likelihood of developing cancer, which is what happens to people with certain mutations in POT1. Doctors and scientists can develop a pedigree based on this information, which is a chart used to examine which family members have a disease.

Evelina: Can you tell us how you connected POT1 to telomere length?

DA: We had information on their telomeres from experiments we'd done on material from those patients, and it was lining up perfectly with the data that we were getting from the saturation

genome editing, suggesting that we were certainly able to use the saturation genome editing to identify variants that were of clinical importance. And then over the years, we would get emails all the time where a very well-meaning physician was asking us, “What is this variant? Have we seen this before anywhere? Is it disease causing?”, and that really spurred us on to further work on developing saturation genome editing for POT1.

Kortni: How much progress have you made in mutating this gene?

DA: We are about 95% there with finishing POT1, there's a very small region of the gene that we're trying to finish at the moment. And that will complete all of the protein coding regions of POT1. What did we learn from it? Well, the first thing that we did was to resolve some families that we had where we had some evidence that that maybe a variant was associated with the phenotype, but we could show, we could add some function to that variant which, as I said previously, can be used together with other information, like the clinical phenotype by physicians to make decisions about how those patients are managed.

We've also as part of the work that we've done, found regions of POT1 that had not really been described to have function which we can show have a functional role as part of that work. More recently, there's been some evidence that there's a difference between the variants that are acquired in POT1, whether they cause long telomeres, which is what we described previously or in some rare cases they can cause short telomeres. So there's same mutations in the same region of the protein can have these 2 different outputs, and so we're really exploring that at the moment. But that's going to be an interesting output of this work as well.

Evelina: So can you tell us more about how you developed saturation genome editing for POT1?

DA: So originally we started with a very small number of families. We had maybe half a dozen who had variants that we were exploring, where we were trying to see whether the variant that we found in the patient could disrupt the role of POT1. And then we actually engineered mice that carry some of those variants as well to see whether they were more likely to get cancer. And they did. And then we started to think about how we could go really large scale and assess every possible change within the gene. And that's really where saturation genome editing became our our weapon of choice.

Evelina: Saturation genome editing, or SGE, is a technique that uses genetic scissors to cut a part of a gene and insert every possible mutation. SGE makes mutations for all types of variants, including deletions and insertions of bases and as well as regions that are not included in the final protein (these are sometimes called introns). The mutated DNA can be inserted into cells, which are allowed to grow under specific conditions. These conditions can be used to assess the functionality of the mutated protein.

Kortni: DNA sequencing can then reveal which mutations were useful or harmful to the cell, and can be used to produce function “maps” of proteins, similar to the MAVEs which we covered in episode 1 of this podcast. Dr. Adams, what motivated you to use SGE in the first place?

DA: As we did more and more sequencing as part of our work, I became increasingly frustrated that I would identify these variants of uncertain significance and I couldn't really define what what they were doing and whether they were important or not. And so then I started looking around for methods that I could use to explore the variance that we're identifying. And so we tried these kind of cDNA rescue experiments, and they kind of worked, but we could never get all of the variants that we wanted. So I wanted to not just explore single variants, but actually do everything and preemptively identify the function of variants. And it so happened that at the time my colleague, Matt Hurles, who's now the director of the Sanger, sat down next to me at a meeting and said “I'm interested in this method called Saturation Genome Editing.” There are a lot of missense variants of uncertain significance that we didn't really know the function of, and we managed to resolve them.

Evelina: Why are scientists so interested in making more of these maps?

DA: I think the value is that when you generate a sequence function map, you're doing so without any priors. So you're doing so where you're asking the question about all of the possible variants within the gene, you get a very broad spectrum view of what particular variants do within that gene, and you can therefore explore biology in a way that you wouldn't normally do, and that kind of breadth of exploration allows you to find things you wouldn't expect. For example, synonymous alterations that might change the function of the gene, or maybe bits of the gene or protein that are regulatory, that you didn't know that they were and things like that which aren't initially the output of many experiments that we and others have done in the past.

Kortni: Unexpected discoveries are the best part of doing research! How do you see SGE being applied in a clinical setting?

DA: The vision that we would have is that we would like to do all of the 114 cancer predisposition genes that are regularly tested for in clinical genetics, because I think that that would be a really useful reference set for the cancer genetics community, the clinical genetics community, and also for all of the people who are fundamentally interested in how those genes work and contribute to biology. That's what our vision is. And we're working on other genes, genes like DICER1 and RAD51C, we're working on as well in the same way to really understand the biology of those genes.

Evelina: Science only seems easy when we are presenting it, what are some challenges with SGE that you are currently facing?

DA: I think the challenge is really dealing with the scale, you need an enormous amount of will to perform these sorts of experiments, as you know well. It's large scale experiment, it involves a lot of synthesising segments of DNA, and that has its challenges both logistically and also financially, to a degree. You need highly skilled individuals to do the cell culture and to analyze the data as well. But actually, it's not an insurmountable problem, and I think that, you know, the value of generating the data at scale systematically is so huge, that this is a challenge we want to pick up and take forward.

Over time, we will also work with our colleagues who use approaches like machine learning to help us improve our experiments and for us to help them improve their predictions. I think that the two communities will come together over time. I think that the real challenge, then, is going to be how we provide the data that we generate in a format that clinical geneticists can then pick up and use for the very important decisions that they make.

Kortni: You may have heard that high school students are using ChatGPT and other artificial intelligence programs to write their essays for them, but scientists are trying to teach similar programs to predict the outcomes of their experiments.

Evelina: So we have learned about the negative effects of mutations in POT1, and about SGE being used to explore its function. What about the other genes that affect a person's risk for developing melanoma?

DA: CDKN2A is involved in regulation of cell cycle checkpoints, and the cell cycle in general. And those patients get melanoma principally, but they can also get malignancies like pancreatic cancer. Whereas BAP1 which we've also worked on, these patients will get a type of melanoma in the eye called uveal melanoma. They can get melanoma in the skin, but also other types of cancer, such as a type in the liver which is called cholangiocarcinoma.

Kortni: How did you first get involved with studying BAP1?

DA: Yeah. So BAP1 was really interesting to us, because it's known to be involved in predisposition to uveal melanoma, so melanoma that occurs within the eye. And I was really intrigued by why it was uveal melanoma, which is such a rare malignancy. Why is it that germline changes in BAP1 contribute to disease risk? And as you know, melanoma, malignancies that occur within the eye are particularly challenging to treat, and so really knowing which individuals, which patients have a change in the BAP1 gene, and are therefore predisposed, is very, very important in terms of managing them and indeed their family.

Evelina: BAP1 is an important enzyme that removes a small protein tag called ubiquitin from histones, which are used to compress DNA so that it fits into your cells.

Kortni: Yeah, It helps regulate the degree to which DNA is unwound, and therefore whether it is available to give instructions for protein production. Mutations in BAP1 can cause a number of negative effects, as we will see shortly.

DA: So it really started with a single individual who walked into the clinic, one of our melanoma clinics that we're associated with and we sequenced him as part of the project that we were involved in. And we found that he had a variant of uncertain significance that fell into the BAP1 gene, and that was work that was done by Daniela, who was my PhD Student at the time. We were working with Julia Newton-Bishop and Tim Bishop who were based in Leeds on those studies. And then Andrew Waters came into my group, he was basically this force of nature starting these experiments to really explore BAP1.

Evelina: Is BAP1 involved in other phenotypes as well?

DA: It's fascinating, but BAP1 is also involved in a neurodevelopmental phenotype as well. And what work that we've done has shown is that the variants actually appear to have the same sort of function. So they appear to be loss of function in both the cancer predisposing syndrome, but also in the neurodevelopmental disorder as well. And that's interesting because we don't quite understand why, essentially the same mutation can end up in these 2 different conditions. So maybe that's got something to do with other genetics of the of those individuals, those patients. Hence, why, it's really important to identify which variants are disease-causing so that we can better look after those people and their families.

Kortni: How many more genes do you think will be discovered to have a role in melanoma development?

DA: I guess so far we've managed to identify about half of them. I think we're now getting to a point where we can identify rarer variants in small numbers of families. So CDKN2A, POT1 and BAP1 contribute to about half, and then there looks like there's a whole spectrum of additional genes and mutations that can contribute as well.

Kortni: That was great, thank you for speaking to us today, Dr Adams.

Evelina: We just learned that skin tone and some germline variants such as CDKN2A, POT1 and BAP1 genes can highly predispose some families to cancer. Our next specialist is working with sporadic melanoma risk. As opposed to Dr. Adams, she focuses on common genetic variants.

Kortni: Hello Dr. Choi, can you introduce yourself?

Dr. Jiyeon Choi: My name is Jiyeon Choi and I'm an investigator at the National Cancer Institute in Maryland in the US. I did my postdoctoral study with Doctor Kevin Brown at the NCI where I focused on studying genetic susceptibility to melanoma. During my postdoctoral training, I adopted a lot of functional genomics tools to address this topic, and as an independent investigator, I continued some of the Melanoma studies including the high-throughput variant characterization that we talk about today.

Evelina: How many cancer cases are caused by inherited mutations? Do they make up a large number of people diagnosed?

JC: I would say around 90% of melanoma cases are without any multi case family history and we call these sporadic melanoma cases. So, in those cases, it's not like one very high impact variant is causing melanoma in these individuals. So, the hypothesis is that multiple common genetic variants which have individually small effect sizes, but when they kind of accumulate a lot in an individual they might contribute to melanoma risk. So, people who have a lot of those variants might develop melanoma even with the similar amount of exposure [to people who don't develop melanoma].

Kortni: What kind of studies are used to associate the risk of many variants with melanoma? How do we know that these mutations are contributing to the development of this disease and its not due to random chance?

JC: So to test this hypothesis and discover these risk-associated common variants, we can use GWAS ...

Kortni: or Genome-wide association studies...

JC: ... and basically how it works is that we recruit a lot of melanoma patients and because the effect size of each variant is very small, we need a large sample size to be able to detect these signals. So typically, nowadays, people have like tens of thousands or, or even more hundreds of thousands of cases. But it really depends on the prevalence of the disease.

So the most recent melanoma GWAS had 36,000 cases of people who have melanoma and typically they recruit a similar number or much higher number of control individuals who don't have any type of cancer. So, after getting their blood or buccal sample, we can isolate genomic DNA and we can genotype them.

Evelina: Genotypes are the genetic sequence found in a person's DNA, which then goes on to be expressed as one trait or another, which we then observe as a phenotype, which we already mentioned earlier.

JC: In the human genome, there are I think millions of different variants and the most common is a single nucleotide polymorphisms, or SNPs.

Evelina: There are many locations that can have a varied base of the four DNA bases, which Dr. Choi referred to as SNPs.

Kortni: For example, I might have an A base at a certain location, while someone else may have a G base in that same place. These two slightly different sequences of the same gene are called alleles, and when Dr. Choi references the variants she is researching she is talking about these various SNPs.

JC: So, let's say we're detecting a million SNPs across the genome from each participant. And then the key question here is we ask for each and every SNP. Okay, so a SNP typically has two different alleles. So when we look at cases versus controls, we ask if an allele has higher frequencies in cases compared to controls. So that could indicate that, oh, this allele is correlated with the propensity of having melanoma. So we run statistical tests of if the difference is significant for each and every SNP. So basically, we run a million tests because we ask it for every SNP. And after applying a very stringent statistical cutoff, if a SNP passes this cutoff, we declare that as a genome-wide significant variant that is associated with melanoma risk. So far in the most recent study, we identified these significant variants from 54 different places of the genome or 54 loci.

Evelina: So we learned that genome-wide association studies is a technique used to examine the genetic predisposition of a disease in a large population, but how can we know for sure the effect of a detected variant in disease?

JC: Sure, so I explained a little bit about how GWAS works but eQTL or, expression quantitative trait loci, is a very similar concept to GWAS in a way. So for GWAS, we asked the question of which heritable genetic variants are associated with the disease status or other human traits. So, in the case of melanoma and many other diseases, it's disease or no disease, it's binary. But many other human traits are in a continuous scale. So for example, height, weight, BMI or blood lipid levels, those are in a continuous scale. So when we look at gene expression level measured by microarrays or like RNA sequencing, they are also in a continuous level. So there are like 20 to 25,000 different genes in the human genome, but if we treat an expression level of one gene as a single trait, then we can run a similar association analysis. So the question is, which variants are correlated with gene expression?

Evelina: Those variants are what we call "eQTL". The differences in the DNA sequences add up to produce the visible phenotype.

Kortni: So you look at each single gene of the DNA in a cohort of people, to see if there are modifications or single nucleotide polymorphisms (called SNPs) that are affecting how much of a protein is being made?

JC: So, SNPs usually have two different alleles. So let's say there's an A allele and a C allele. So we inherit two chromosomes from our parents, one from mom, one from dad. So we can bin people into three groups, either AA, AC or a CC group. So if you count the allelic dosage, we have this continuous scale of gene expression level. So we can basically investigate the relationship of a SNP and a gene expression level by running a regression. So if there's a correlation, then OK, this SNP is correlated with this gene. So we can do that for all 25 [thousand] genes. So the importance of eQTL in the context of GWAS is you saw the similarity of how we connect genetic variants to either disease status or to expression level of a gene.

Evelina: In summary, when you look at common genetic variants you can infer that if it is associated with disease status and also the expression of this gene, then maybe this gene is contributing to this disease.

JC: So it kind of allows us to understand the mechanism. It's actually the first step of understanding why this region of the genome is highlighted by these variants.

Kortni: So what is the next step?

JC: So, I mentioned that GWAS could identify different regions of the genome or loci, but it doesn't really identify a single variant out of that.

Evelina: That's because a loci has potentially many SNPs!

JC: That means if we find some association of a SNP, we're not just identifying that exact SNP, we're identifying a group of SNPs that are showing similar statistical significance. So that poses a little bit of a challenge in the follow up steps because we don't really know if all of those SNPs are functional or only one or a few of them are functional, but the others just migrate together from from generation to generation. So we need to kind of test them experimentally.

Kortni: Is this what your study did? How do you test all the SNPs experimentally?

JC: Yeah. So, the main thing of the study that we're talking about is adapting the MPRA method, which is massively parallel reporter essays.

Evelina: You mentioned that there are 54 locations in the genome that are implicated in melanoma development, how can you use MPRA to examine their effect?

JC: When I said there are 54 loci that are associated with melanoma, if we count those connected variants, we're talking about like 2000 different variants. So testing 2000 variants, for example, one by one is taxing, and it's almost impossible in a way. But thanks to MPRA, we can actually test hundreds of thousands of different DNA sequences at the same time.

So we generate a construct where these the sequences around these variants are positioned in front of a reporter gene. So when we transfect them into a cell line, they can express themselves, but we can actually detect the expressed molecular barcodes that we can track back to which variant that we were testing. So this allows us to assay the gene regulatory function of each SNP in a single assay at the same time in large scale.

Evelina: In episode 1, we spoke to Dr. Fields in greater detail about MPRA, and their usefulness in detecting disease-causing mutations.

Kortni: Coming back to melanoma, Dr. Choi, can you tell us more about the biology behind this cancer? What is the role of melanocytes in the skin?

JC: So melanocytes are like not like the major cell type in skin, but they are the cells that produce melanin, which is a pigment that is deposited in human skin and it protects us from the damaging effect of ultraviolet radiation. So melanocytes tend to renew themselves in a controlled manner. But when this control is disrupted by mutations and gene expression changes, they can turn into melanoma. So, because GWAS can detect very subtle but consistent effects of common variants on melanoma risk, we need to look at it like in a more kind of zoomed out view.

Evelina: Can you explain how mutations present at birth as well as acquired mutations affect cancer risk?

JC: Melanoma only occurs in later stages of human life, but germline genetic variants that we're connecting to melanoma risk are present from gestation, and at the same time, tumorigenesis is a kind of a typically long multi-step process. So it could take multiple years involving initiation, progression and metastasis and outcome. So, to study the function of melanoma susceptibility genes, we need to consider the biological context before, during and after the malignant transformation of these normal cells. So, in that sense, we wanted to use both non-transformed melanocytes and tumorous melanoma cell lines.

Kortni: And what did you find?

JC: So one of the one of the kind of surprising but very nice findings was about the differences of the variant function based on the cell type that we tested them. So most of the functional variants that we identified through MPRA showed a similar function in both melanoma and melanocyte cell lines. But we saw a small subset being very different between two cell types. So for example, some variants are only functional in melanoma cells, but not in melanocytes. So this kind of suggests that in this tumor-specific environment, including transcription factors that are activated in tumors could affect the melanoma associated variant function.

Evelina: What do you hope your research will accomplish?

JC: So I guess it's there is some short-term and long-term effect in my mind. By using MPRA, we were able to identify hundreds of functional variants, and on top of that, we developed the variant scoring system which incorporates the experimental results from MPRA and all the available public databases about variant annotation, so we were able to assign the scores for each variant.

Kortni: If you want to hear more about scoring variants and variant predictors, make sure to tune in for the fifth episode where we dedicate a whole story to this. But what can this do for melanoma?

JC: So we can kind of have a sense of what are the most plausible variants that could be functional and quote-unquote causal. So, by having that sense and having a better idea of what could be true functional variants among those highly-linked variants, we might be able to contribute to better risk assessment in different populations, for example, because it is considered that those functional and quote-unquote causal variants might be the same across different human populations.

But I guess a bigger part in my mind is that by knowing what's functional variants and what are the target genes of those functional variants, we get to understand the genes that are involved in melanoma genesis. So we have a better idea of etiology, which that knowledge could inform to develop better prediction and prevention and maybe therapy. So it's kind of a long way to go, but I think we're laying the foundation of that process.

Kortni: Thank you for speaking with us today Dr. Choi.

Evelina: We want to thank both Dr. Adams and Dr. Choi for shining a light on the need for variant effect maps in melanoma.

Alex: Today, we explored the basis of genetic modification and cancer risk to melanoma. We learned how large-scale testing can aid in the classification of variants and the basic understanding of the disease biology. Through the use of saturation genome editing and eQTL mapping, our experts were able to interpret the effect of thousands of variants for 3 genes important to melanoma development. These strategies are now being employed for all human genes. If you would like to know more about the efforts to solve variants of uncertain significance, you can learn more through the Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance.

Kortni: But before we go, we have asked some rapid-fire questions to both of our guests.

Moez Dawood: Are you ready?

JC: Yes!

DA: Go for it.

Moez: Alright, DNA or RNA?

DA: DNA

JC: RNA

Moez: R or Python?

DA: R

JC: R

Moez: Short-read or Long-read?

DA: Short-read

JC: Long-read

Moez: Single-cell or Bulk?

DA: Single-cell

JC: Single-cell

Moez: Knock-in or Knock-out?

DA: Knock-out

JC: Knock-out

Moez: Golden Gate or Gibson?

DA: Gibson

JC: Gibson

Moez: Coding or Noncoding?

DA: Coding

JC: Non-coding!

Moez: In vitro or in vivo?

DA: Both

JC: In vivo

Moez: Favorite model organism?

DA: After humans, mouse

JC: Mouse

Moez: Favorite scientist?

DA: Julian Sampson

JC: Gregor Mendel

Moez: Favorite media?

JC: Dermal cell basal medium

Moez: Favorite sequencing technology?

DA: Illumina

JC: Amplicon sequencing

Moez: Favorite piece of lab equipment?

DA: Timer

JC: I love the e-gel machine

Moez: Favorite science movie/media?

DA: I like Gattaca

JC: I like RadioLab podcasts

Moez: Something outside the lab that you wish you could multiplex?

DA: Cooking

JC: Laundry

Moez: What is the smartest thing you've ever done in the lab

JC: Met my wife.

DA: I used rubber bands for the vortexing part of immersion PCRs, that is a critical part of MPRAs.

Moez: Then the last question here is, what is the stupidest thing you've ever done in the lab?

DA: I nearly caused a lab fire in Sydney, when I was a PhD student.

JC: Oh my god so, I accidentally set the lab on fire.

Alex: Okay I hope you enjoyed today's episode, and tune in next time on Variants and Us, where we will discuss testing variants in context.

[Outro music plays]

Episode 2 Show Notes

Further reading on BAP1 in melanoma and other cancers:

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